

Treatment of septic shock complicated by mediastinitis after HeartMate 3 BiVAD implantation using echo-guided device parameter optimization: a case report

Stanislav Georgiev¹, Yordan Makedonski¹, Krasimir Petkov³, Vera Tabakova⁴, Dimitar Petkov¹

1 Department of Cardiac Surgery, St. Ekaterina University Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, St. Ekaterina University Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria

3 Department of Cardiology, St. Ekaterina University Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Department of Clinical Microbiology, St. Ekaterina University Hospital, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Stanislav Georgiev (stanislav5111@gmail.com)

Received 7 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 22 January 2026 ♦ Published 3 February 2026

Citation: Georgiev S, Pampulova L, Abedinov P, Iliev R, Makedonski Y, Petkov K, Tabakova V, Petkov D (2026) Treatment of septic shock complicated by mediastinitis after HeartMate 3 BiVAD implantation using echo-guided device parameter optimization: a case report. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e184514>

Abstract

Introduction: Septic shock complicated by poststernotomy mediastinitis in patients with mechanical circulatory support devices is a rare and life-threatening condition associated with high mortality. Management is particularly challenging because of the presence of prosthetic material and the risk of device contamination.

Case presentation: We report a 63-year-old man with end-stage nonischemic cardiomyopathy who underwent HeartMate 3 biventricular assist device (BiVAD) implantation as bridge-to-transplant therapy. Four weeks after discharge, he was readmitted with septic shock, multiorgan failure, and mediastinitis. Treatment included broad-spectrum empirical antimicrobial therapy followed by targeted de-escalation, repeated surgical debridement with prolonged vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) therapy, continuous renal replacement therapy, and individualized echocardiography-guided optimization of BiVAD pump parameters to improve systemic perfusion. Device explantation was avoided. During rehabilitation, orthostatic collapse due to posture-dependent preload insufficiency was diagnosed using upright transesophageal echocardiography and resolved through targeted pump flow adjustment.

Conclusion: This case demonstrates that severe septic shock and mediastinitis in BiVAD-supported patients can be successfully managed without device removal through multidisciplinary care, antimicrobial stewardship, VAC therapy, and dynamic echocardiography-guided device optimization.

Keywords

Biventricular assist device, mechanical circulatory support, mediastinitis, septic shock, vacuum-assisted closure

Introduction

Septic shock remains a major cause of mortality despite advances in critical care, particularly when complicated by deep sternal wound infection. Poststernotomy mediastinitis is associated with prolonged hospitalization and mortality rates reaching 40–50%. (Singh et al. 2011) Management becomes especially complex in patients with mechanical circulatory support (MCS) devices because of the presence of prosthetic material, the increased risk of biofilm formation, and limited options for device explantation.

The HeartMate 3 biventricular assist device (BiVAD) provides advanced circulatory support for patients with end-stage heart failure. However, artificial circulatory support imposes physiological constraints during septic shock, as the ability to rapidly augment cardiac output in response to increased metabolic demands is limited compared with native cardiac function.

Vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) therapy has become an effective adjunct in the management of deep sternal wound infections, promoting drainage and wound healing. Antimicrobial therapy must be carefully selected and dynamically adjusted, considering altered pharmacokinetics in critically ill patients and the risk of device-related infection.

We present a case of severe septic shock and mediastinitis caused by *Escherichia coli* in a patient with an implanted HeartMate 3 BiVAD, successfully managed through combined surgical and targeted antimicrobial therapy, prolonged VAC treatment, and individualized echocardiography-guided optimization of device parameters.

Case presentation

A 63-year-old man with end-stage nonischemic cardiomyopathy was urgently transferred from another healthcare facility in critical condition. At admission, he was mechanically ventilated, sedated with continuous midazolam infusion, and receiving high-dose vasopressor and catecholamine support because of severe hemodynamic instability, complicated by recurrent episodes of ventricular tachycardia requiring repeated defibrillations. Because of the critical state, a comprehensive preoperative neurocognitive and social assessment was not possible. The immediate clinical priority was stabilization, rhythm control, and restoration of adequate systemic perfusion.

Following initial stabilization, the patient underwent implantation of a HeartMate 3 biventricular assist device as bridge-to-transplant therapy. The postoperative course was uncomplicated, and he was discharged in stable condition.

Four weeks later, the patient was readmitted in poor general condition with hypothermia (34 °C), tachypnea, chest pain, fatigue, purulent secretion from the upper sternotomy wound, and acute kidney injury progressing to anuria. On presentation, he was somnolent (Glasgow Coma Scale score of 8), hypotensive, and ex-

hibited signs of multiorgan failure. Laboratory findings (Table 1) demonstrated severe systemic inflammatory response and coagulopathy. A Sequential Organ Failure Assessment score exceeding 12 points indicated extremely high predicted mortality (> 95.2%) (Singer et al. 2016).

The patient was intubated, and continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT) was initiated. A CytoSorb filter was used to reduce circulating inflammatory mediators and vasopressor requirements. Because of significant hepatic dysfunction and high bleeding risk, systemic anticoagulation was withheld during the initial phase of treatment.

Table 1. Laboratory findings at admission.

Parameter	Value
Leukocytes	55 × 10 ⁹ /L
Platelets	12 × 10 ⁹ /L
C-reactive protein	218.6 mg/L
Procalcitonin	2.75 ng/mL
Interleukin-6	227.83 pg/mL (peak 953.3 pg/mL)
INR	9.11
Blood urea nitrogen	23 mmol/L
Serum creatinine	187 μmol/L
SOFA score	> 12 points
National Early Warning Score 2 (NEWS2)	19 points
eGFR	32 mL/min/1.73 m ² G3b class

Microbiology and imaging

Blood cultures and wound swabs obtained at admission yielded growth of *Escherichia coli*. Identical susceptibility profiles in blood and wound samples supported a common infectious source. Additionally, the pathogen was identified in tracheal secretion.

The patient had a history of chronic fistulous paraproctitis with previous isolation of *E. coli*, suggesting a possible origin.

Contrast-enhanced computed tomography of the chest revealed a localized anterior mediastinal abscess consistent with poststernotomy mediastinitis. No radiologic evidence of involvement of BiVAD components, including cannulas, driveline, or pump housing, was identified (Figs 1, 2). Positron emission tomography-computed tomography was considered but not performed because of the patient's critical condition and the risks associated with intrahospital transport.

Antimicrobial management

Empirical therapy

Given the profound severity of septic shock and the concomitant presence of a mechanical circulatory support device, broad-spectrum empirical antimicrobial therapy was promptly initiated immediately following the collection of appropriate microbiological specimens. The

Figure 1. A. Three-dimensional reconstruction of a CT scan of a patient with a BiVAD; B. Coronal view of the CT scan. Both images show device localization.

Figure 2. Axial CT image revealing structural alterations in the sternal bone (orange arrow).

empirical regimen consisted of meropenem, teicoplanin, and colistin, selected to ensure comprehensive coverage against a wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens, including multidrug-resistant organisms commonly encountered in critically ill patients. Antimicrobial dosing was carefully individualized, taking into

consideration the use of continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT), as well as the significant pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic alterations associated with critical illness, such as increased volume of distribution, altered drug clearance, and organ dysfunction. (Thalhammer et al. 1998; Sun et al. 2025) Therapeutic

decisions were continuously reassessed and adjusted as clinically indicated, based on microbiological results and the patient's evolving clinical status.

Pathogen-directed therapy and antimicrobial stewardship

Following confirmation of *E. coli* susceptibility to fluoroquinolones, antimicrobial therapy was promptly de-escalated. Meropenem and colistin were discontinued to reduce nephrotoxicity and antimicrobial resistance pressure. Targeted therapy with ciprofloxacin was initiated, while teicoplanin was temporarily continued during active wound management and VAC therapy. The patient received three weeks of intravenous therapy followed by prolonged oral treatment for a total duration of two months. Renal function gradually recovered, allowing discontinuation of CRRT and adjustment of antimicrobial dosing.

Considerations in BiVAD patients undergoing CRRT

Antimicrobial management in BiVAD-supported patients undergoing CRRT is challenging because of altered drug distribution, clearance, and tissue penetration, as well as the risk of biofilm formation on prosthetic material.

To enhance systemic perfusion and antibiotic delivery during septic shock, BiVAD pump flow was gradually increased under echocardiographic guidance to approximate a hyperdynamic circulatory response.

Surgical management and vacuum-assisted closure therapy

Surgical treatment focused on effective source control while preserving the integrity of the implanted BiVAD system. The patient underwent repeated surgical debridement with removal of necrotic tissue.

VAC therapy was initiated immediately following debridement and maintained at a continuous negative pressure of -100 to -120 mmHg. This approach facilitated effective drainage and granulation tissue formation without the need for device explantation or reconstructive procedures. Complete secondary wound closure was achieved after six weeks (Fig. 5).

Orthostatic collapse and upright transesophageal echocardiography

During early rehabilitation, following significant fluid removal and a weight reduction of approximately 20 kg, the patient developed recurrent orthostatic collapse within 30 seconds of assuming an upright position. Symptoms were absent in the supine position (Fig. 3), and routine device interrogation suggested stable BiVAD function at rest.

Dynamic upright transesophageal echocardiography in the sedated and intubated patient revealed posture-de-

Figure 3. Color Doppler showing normal blood flow through the LVAD inflow cannula in the supine position.

pendent left ventricular wall suction with transient inflow cannula obstruction, consistent with preload insufficiency (Fig. 4). Management included cautious volume optimiza-

tion, gradual mobilization, and echocardiography-guided adjustment of BiVAD pump flow parameters in the upright position. Orthostatic symptoms resolved completely.

Figure 4. Echocardiography of a BiVAD patient. The green arrow indicates the LVAD inflow cannula. The blue arrow highlights the ventricular wall being suctioned into the cannula. On the right, Doppler imaging demonstrates markedly reduced—almost absent—blood flow through the cannula.

A

B

Figure 5. A. Granulation of the wound after VAC therapy; B. Secondary closure after six weeks.

Discussion

This case highlights several significant challenges inherent in the management of patients supported with mechanical circulatory devices. First, the physiological hemodynamic response to infection is often blunted or absent because of the presence of artificial circulation, which lacks the typical hyperdynamic state observed in septic shock and can delay clinical recognition or response. Second, the patient's marked fluid overload further compromised both systemic circulation and pulmonary gas exchange, exacerbating hemodynamic instability and impairing oxygenation. To approximate the hyperdynamic circulatory response typically seen in septic patients, pump flow was deliberately increased under echocardiographic guidance, with adjustments performed in the upright position to optimize cardiac filling and output while minimizing adverse effects.

Conclusion

Septic shock complicated by mediastinitis in patients supported with a biventricular assist device is rare and life-threatening. Successful resolution without device explantation can be achieved through multidisciplinary care, antimicrobial stewardship, VAC therapy, and dynamic echocardiography-guided device optimization. Upright transesophageal echocardiography may be a valuable tool for identifying posture-dependent hemodynamic compromise during recovery.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- Singer M, Deutschman CS, Seymour CW, Shankar-Hari M, Annane D, Bauer M, Bellomo R, Bernard GR, Chiche J-D, Coopersmith CM, Hotchkiss RS, Levy MM, Marshall JC, Martin GS, Opal SM, Rubenfeld GD, van der Poll T, Vincent J-L, Angus DC (2016) The Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock (Sepsis-3). *JAMA* 315: 801–810. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2016.0287>
- Singh K, Anderson E, Harper JG (2011) Overview and Management of Sternal Wound Infection. *Seminars in Plastic Surgery* 25: 025–033. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0031-1275168>
- Sun Q, Jian J, Zhou X, Hong Z, Yang S, Zheng Y, Wang S, Zhao M (2025) Population pharmacokinetics of teicoplanin and dosage optimization in sepsis patients based on continuous renal replacement therapy. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 16: 1621959. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2025.1621959>
- Thalhammer F, Schenk P, Burgmann H, El Menyawi I, Hollenstein UM, Rosenkranz AR, Sunder-Plassmann G, Breyer S, Ratheiser K (1998) Single-dose pharmacokinetics of meropenem during continuous venovenous hemofiltration. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy* 42: 2417–2420. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.42.9.2417>

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Ethic commission of University Hospital Saint Ekaterina. Written informed consent for publication was obtained from the patient.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

Manuscript editing.

Funding

No external funding was received.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to patient management, manuscript drafting, and approval of the final version.

Author ORCIDs

Stanislav Georgiev [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-2900-9297) <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-2900-9297>

Rumen Iliev [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4115-0219) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4115-0219>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.